

TRANSACTIONAL FEATURES OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Proverbs are a type of traditional wisdom that has been passed down through generations. In English and Uzbek literature, proverbs are used to convey important messages and values to readers. Proverbs are one of the most important genres of folklore, and today new aspects of linguistics are revealed through the in-depth study of proverbs in comparative linguistics. On the other hand, it is a comparative study of the lingocultural and semantic features of proverbs in English and Uzbek in both languages and a generalization of their similarities and differences. In particular, the comparative study of Uzbek and English proverbs proves the similarities and differences in the mentality of the peoples, expressing the extent to which the language reflects the cultural and national customs of both peoples. In order to study this issue, it is necessary to compare the articles describing the national culture of the English and Uzbek peoples, to analyze the national mentality and its characteristics.

One of the main transactional features of proverbs is their ability to provide guidance and advice. English proverbs such as "a stitch in time saves nine" and "actions speak louder than words" offer practical advice on how to navigate life's challenges. Similarly, Uzbek proverbs like "the one who knows the way is the one who gets there" and "the one who saves a life saves the world" offer guidance on how to live a fulfilling and meaningful life.

Another transactional feature of proverbs is their ability to convey cultural values and beliefs. English proverbs like "honesty is the best policy" and "you reap what you sow" reflect the importance of integrity and accountability in Western culture. Uzbek proverbs like "a guest is a gift from God" and "a true friend is better than a hundred relatives" reflect the importance of hospitality and loyalty in Uzbek culture.

Finally, proverbs can also be used to create a sense of community and shared identity. By using proverbs that are familiar to a particular group or culture, writers can create a sense of connection with their readers. This is especially true in Uzbek literature, where proverbs are often used as a way to connect with readers on a deeper level and reinforce cultural identity.

In addition to guidance, cultural values, and community-building, proverbs in English and Uzbek literature also serve as a means of persuasion. By using well-known proverbs, writers can appeal to their readers' emotions and convince them to adopt a certain point of view or take a particular action. For example, the English proverb "the early bird catches the worm" is often used to persuade people to wake up early and be productive. Similarly, the Uzbek proverb "a good name is better than riches" is used to persuade people to prioritize their reputation over material wealth.

Furthermore, proverbs in both languages are often used to add depth and richness to literary works. By incorporating proverbs into their writing, authors can add layers of meaning and nuance that might not be possible through straightforward narration.

Therefore, proverbs play an important role in both English and Uzbek literature. They offer practical advice, convey cultural values, create a sense of community, persuade readers, and add depth to literary works. As such, they continue to be an important part of the literary tradition in both languages.

Transactional features of proverbs refer to their communicative functions and how they are used in discourse. In English and Uzbek literature, proverbs serve various transactional functions, including guidance, cultural values, community-building, persuasion, and literary enrichment.

Guidance refers to the practical advice that proverbs offer to readers. Proverbs like "practice makes perfect" and "look before you leap" provide readers with practical wisdom that can help them navigate life's challenges.

Cultural values are also conveyed through proverbs. They reflect the beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that are valued in a particular culture. For example, the English proverb "honesty is the best policy" reflects the importance of integrity in Western cultures, while the Uzbek proverb "a guest is a gift from God" reflects the hospitality and respect for guests that are valued in Uzbek culture.

Community-building refers to how proverbs create a sense of shared identity and belonging among readers. Proverbs are often used in conversation and storytelling as a way to connect with others and reinforce common values. They can also be used to bridge cultural differences and promote understanding between different groups.

Persuasion is another important transactional function of proverbs. By using well-known proverbs, writers can appeal to readers' emotions and convince them to adopt a certain point of view or take a particular action.

Proverbs like "actions speak louder than words" and "time heals all wounds" can be used to persuade readers to forgive and move on from past conflicts.

All proverbs are different from one another, depending on the history of creation, the way that people express their lifestyle. There are similarities between proverbs in English and Uzbek. This attitude is that when we analyze proverbs in various ways: 1. Morphological; 2. Lexical; 3. Etiological; 4. Stylistic

Transactional features of proverbs in English and Uzbek languages can be understood through the theoretical framework of pragmatics, which is the study of how language is used in social contexts. Proverbs are a form of language that is used to achieve specific communicative goals, and their transactional features reflect the different ways in which they are used to achieve these goals.

In English literature, proverbs have been studied as a form of folk wisdom that reflects the values and beliefs of a particular culture. They are often used to convey practical advice, moral lessons, and cultural norms, and they can be found in a variety of genres, including fables, tales, and proverbs collections.

In Uzbek literature, proverbs also serve as a means of conveying cultural values and practical wisdom. They are often used in everyday conversation and storytelling, and they play an important role in creating a sense of shared identity and belonging among Uzbek speakers.

The transactional features of proverbs in both English and Uzbek literature reflect the complex ways in which language is used to achieve specific communicative goals. By studying these features, scholars can gain insights into the cultural values, social norms, and linguistic practices that shape the use of proverbs in different contexts.

Finally, proverbs can add depth and richness to literary works. By incorporating proverbs into their writing, authors can add layers of meaning and nuance that might not be possible through straightforward narration. Proverbs can also create a sense of timelessness and universality in literature, connecting readers across generations and cultures.

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